

Analysis of role of Advertising on gaining Customer Satisfaction: an study based on Paint Industry of Pakistan

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Abstract

this study is made to provide deeper relation of Advertisement efforts on the customer satisfaction in Paint Industry. Therefore, this survey based study is specifically focused on one company. The extensive survey has been conducted to determine the primary response of the general buyers of Paint products. The responses then have been statistically analyzed using one sample T test. The study has concluded that Advertisement made by firms in paint Industry has positive effect on the customer satisfaction. The survey based study has concluded that the advertisements made by firms in paint Industry are highly creative and effective in filling the gap between customer and the firm's management. It has been concluded that advertisement effectiveness can be acquired by being honest in Advertisement i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads. The effective Advertisement efforts can lead to enhance customer satisfaction and hence it may lead to Growth in sales. However, the respondents do not appear comfortable with price being charged.

Keywords. Advertisement, customer satisfaction, Creative Ads

Introduction

In today's competitive market where business compete for customers, however advertising industry plays a key role to market the product and achieve customer satisfaction. Advertising works as a differentiator and has become a key element to form a business planning strategy since January 2000 in Pakistan Media Market. After the advertisement and consume the product by the customer a customer satisfaction not only create loyalty among the customers but it increases the goodwill of the company by uplifting the market value of the brand.

In Pakistan there are many advertising companies are working to serve with the best ideas which represent the theme of product and created customer satisfaction to force customer for repeat buying.

The medium of advertisement used to achieve target market & promote the products however the relation between of customer satisfaction on the basis of advertisement is directly proportional. It is important to consistently measure and monitor the results of advertisements from authentic rating companies working in Pakistan. Without an effective advertisement, customer satisfaction, the company will be losing business as well as spend huge amount on marketing, missing the opportunities and diverse itself at a competitive disadvantage. In order to take the results of how advertising effect on customer satisfaction the Survey has to be carried out.

Problem Statement

Many studies have been on the subject of relation between advertisement and sales revenue. However, there are rarely studies available focusing on effect on satisfaction level due to advertisement. This study is specifically designed to determine the effect of advertisement on the satisfaction of customers.

Review of Literature

The focus of the study by Andreassen and Lindestad (1998) was the relationship of equity in three dimensions customer (value - brand equity and relationship) has been studied in terms of customer satisfaction. The data were selected 200 customers from fast food companies are divided into three groups cafes, restaurants and fast food in Isfahan were collected by Related and alternative randomized. A structural equation model was used to test six hypotheses using the data value by the AMOS software - supported analysis of brand management and account are an important factor to increase customer satisfaction. The study also confirmed the relationship between satisfaction gains by an advertisement.

Thakur and Sing (2012) examined the relationship between brand satisfaction and loyalty among those selected for study in India central brand Cosmetics Company was study. The study examines five benefits of branding, improve. Functional, Social, Symbolic and Appearance data from 150 men and 150 women clients experience these brands was selected products regularly. The results showed significant results 3 and 2 insignificant results. The logo can build customer satisfaction.

Pozo, Teodoro and Tachizawa (2011) made a case study on the impact of the brand on customer loyalty, the purpose of the study, the influence of the study of brand personality (or negatively positively) on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty using five reasons restaurant scale brand personality examined in this study using the model of the six traditional restaurant. The data collection questioner were used. This study confirms five personality aspects of intensive tourist restaurants. Emotions will directly affect customer satisfaction and brand loyalty, as suggested by the results of the constant additions entrepreneurs will increase

Taleghani Largani and Mousavian (2011) examined the impact of the dimensions of the mark on service quality and customer satisfaction in new projects Iran, studying common framework of analysis. Objective of the study, a view imperial relationship of the brand to the customer study was in 2011 that customers discuss the quality of the brand relationship (trust, commitment and satisfaction brand inspired attempts made. gains were collected and structural data from 258 respondents Tehran, Iran analyzed. important research results show the direct relationship between the brand experience equestrian sport model, satisfaction and trust in brands include loyalty. The help explain how to study the results of research spending on branding and marketing activities to build. Term customer relationships with satisfaction by measuring an advertising effects.

Extensive research conducted by Dolat Abadi, Kabiry and Forghani (2013) has collected McDonalds, branding impact McDonald in the direction of customer retention , primary data were Related and alternative and secondary data were observed by magazines newspapers and collected various items, there were 100 people , research involved in most of them were women 54 respondents between 17-25 years. The partial least squares method was developed in this study, which showed that the strength used an optimistic effect on customer loyalty. Less than 7 hypothesis tests alone were accepted, while the other four were released from them. Was the results of this study , overall 58.4 per cent of clients were loyal to the brand McDonald and customer satisfaction with the remaining 41.6 per cent were influenced by several factors .

Bloemer and Kasper (1994) worked on their research paper, such as customer satisfaction leads to brand loyalty in this research paper, theoretical and operational definition of customer satisfaction can be found. Data were collected by means of an advertisement in several newspapers and magazines in which the question who wanted to participate in the purchase behavior of products of different customers. Eight hundred sixty-one were returned Eight hundred and thirty eight Related and alternative were used in the analysis. The author has different scales used in the study. In questions, the last Related and alternative respondents, writing was the name of the brand, they know how much they were satisfied or dissatisfied with the brand then. It uses the correlation method . The study concluded that the method clearly true satisfaction of brand loyalty . Therefore, they concluded that the increased amount of evident satisfaction has a strong influence on the brand loyalty. So optimistic that the results of this study was that the management of each company should be more involved and promises of loyalty binds to continue with the product. Customers

Ghafoor, Iqbal, Tariq and Murtaza (2012). is obtained using consumer data Gujranwala , Pakistan , saw , to analyze the impact . Satisfaction of branding and brand loyalty with random data from different universities (University of Punjab, University of gifts and Indus Industries) and local consumer survey was conducted for this purpose. In time and the sample size of 200 respondents months , encouraging the authors use the SPSS software using different statistical methods. The conclusion of this research shows that there is a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty to the brand. In addition, the study found that clients brand while brand determine to ensure complete satisfaction. This can be achieved by accurate positioning. Implications and restrictions and regulations are also part of his " paper.

Rashid (2013) highlight the implications of branding brand loyalty with the most important role to satisfy customers . The authors have worked on several features and advantages of the brand.. In short, research on wireless Telecommunication sektorvon Pakistan together. To this end, a quantitative study was made. Sahiwal colleges and selected for the survey and the questionnaire was distributed universities. Regression and correlation were used to analyze the data. The main objective of this research is to examine the role of branding in providing customer satisfaction , brand image and brand loyalty in relationships and the impact of customer satisfaction determine loyalty. Instrument of this study was reliably with the Cronbach alpha value . 849 There are three hypotheses tested in this study. In any event , namely H1 , H2 and H3 tests (because significant figure) will be accepted.

Saeednia and Sohani (2013) examined the effect of brand satisfaction and overall fidelity, the main objective of the study is to determine the effectiveness of brand image on customer satisfaction in the bottom of the guard .The study was conducted in 2007 in Malaysia. They inspected the five branding benefits. When she began to examine 97 women from different geographical regions of the 97 women were conducted mainly in the not married. Man The result showed that two of the benefits of branding improved performance and function will have a significant impact on the intention of loyalty and secondly, symbolic, experimental and social benefits have a negative impact on the customer loyalty.

Kotler and Zaltman (1971) organized the study in Seoul , she explores the role of the part of the product of the relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty achieved by an creative advertisement link . The purpose of this article is how the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty changes by participating product knowledge. 4592 consumers were randomly selected and contacted by telephone interviews with Personal observation the best companies in the market. 2056 were closed for about cosmetic Related and alternative people and Related and alternative 2058 concerning household goods have been completed. The average respondent was 35 years old . Beyond the coefficients of the high and low participation means a number of groups of analysis was used. The results of the study, companies should focus on brand advertising, advertising, promotions, and influence to increase the product.

Suh and Yi (2006) condusted research in Iran Tehran, the capital of the purpose of this study is to provide an empirical test to analyze the behavior. Impact of CSR on the growing reputation and create brand value of customer satisfaction They used structural equation modeling to test the hypothesis . They hypothesized five years, where she wanted to know if what the CSR activities have an effect on the satisfaction of the brand value of the bank's customers. They designed Related and alternative 384 and 384 employees of the Iranian bank based distributed in the city. Tehran According to their results, this was optimistic impact of CSR on consumer satisfaction , and there was also a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and firmly. Although their study did not confirm that CSR has had a positive impact on the company , organization or brand value .

Akbar and Azhar (2009) conducted to find the image of the relationship, the study of the beliefs of the brand, brand satisfaction and brand value in the field of mobile phones. Primary data were collected by Related and alternative with the size of the sample of 278 mobile phone users molded Region Sukkur. There were four variables in this study, the value of a brand is the dependent variable, while the brand image, satisfaction and brand trust was the dependent variable. The data were analyzed using SPSS software. The majority of people between 15 and 25 years. Six brands are seeking, Nokia, Samsung, Q Mobile, Sony Ericson, Motorola, China Mob, Blackberry, Iphone were selected. They used the method of correlation for the results. The results showed that 68 percent of the population of Sukkur formed were Nokia and the rest 32 per cent was with different brands. Thus, the result of this investigation, it was proposed that all manufacturers of different mobile phones must be on the development of three basic factors that much attention branding and ownership of the trust of the brand of pay satisfaction.

Research Hypotheses

H1: The highly creative Ads are also highly successful.

H2: Consumers have favorable response to the Advertisement efforts of a firm

H3: There is Honesty in Ads i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads

H4: The highly attractive Ads are also highly successful.

H5: The Ads attracts the perception and makes customer sense of comfortable

H6: The Ads by a firm induces to Buy Decision

H7: Physical appearance of the product such as Packaging is highly attractive to induce for Buying

H8: The quality of the Product is on the same line as it appears in the Advertisement and Promotional efforts

H9: Consumers are satisfied with the quality of the product

H10: Consumers are comfortable with the price of the product

H11: The Advertisement has filled gap between consumers and the management of the company

Research Methods

Primary Source of Data

This research is designed to test the customer satisfaction by the effects of an advertisements. The study is based on primary source of data. A well designed questionnaire has been designed to collect the information. The questionnaire is based on Likert scale of 5 values.

Sample size

A sample of 300 respondents has taken from the population of Karachi, Pakistan. The respondents include businessmen, professionals and students who were actively involved in purchase of Paint products. The survey had done in Karachi famous whole sale markets Paint authorized company dealers, by explaining them the reason for the survey by shown the educational documents requested the people to please cooperate.

Statistical technique

The survey results have been analyzed using one sample T Test using SPSS. This test is used to compare the response of respondents with desired test value. Here, the Test Value is 4 representing code of "Agree".

Results

Initial questions were focused on determining the demographics and the general view about the Paint Products. The results of these questions have been summarized as follows using descriptive study.

Table 1 Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	under 18	6	2.2	2.2	2.2
	19-24	27	8.9	8.9	11.1
	25-34	189	63.3	63.3	74.4
	35-44	69	23.3	23.3	97.8
	45-54	6	2.2	2.2	100.0
Total		300	100	100.0	

As my personal analysis in relation with the above mentioned results, mostly customers who generally goes to purchase paints are 25 to above 34 ages for their home usage is and for others, it reflects 63.3%, the second highest is 35 to 44 has a percentage of 23.3%, from 19 to 24. In third position 8.9%, under 18 & from 45 to 54 having the same percentage 2.2 respectively

Table 2 Income

What is your average household income, before tax?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	35,000-49,999	213	71.1	71.1	71.1
	50,000-74,999	87	28.9	28.9	100
	Total	300	100	100	

Mostly the candidates who filled the survey questionnaires having their Income level from 35k to 50, it contain the 71.1 percent and the frequency is 64, the second level is 50k to 75k it has a percentage of 28.9.

This chart will not be effect on the research however the amount of income of any one it will remain to bias.

Table 3 Previous Advertisements

In the past days, how many times have you seen an advertisement made by firms in paint Industry					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	15	4.4	4.4	4.4
	2	39	13.3	13.3	17.8
	3	246	82.2	82.2	100
	Total	300	100	100	

Mostly the candidates who filled forms are working people, either business man or employe any where. The most voted who watched 3 time an ad were 82.2% percent, , however the second on 2 time who watched an ad were 13.3% percent, remaining who never watched an ad 4.4% percent. This dada will help us to analyze the level of effect from an advertisement a customer have achieved.

Table 4 Products related to paint

Have you ever used products related to paint					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	276	92.2	92.2	92.2
	no	24	7.8	7.8	100
	Total	300	100	100	

Out of 300 candidates, those who have used the product after watched an advertisement or inspired, the quality by fulfilling the brand promise were 92.2% percent, however those candidates did not use were 7.8% percent. The results charts shown the level of significance higher with customer satisfaction.

Table 5 comparison

How would you compare this ad with other paint products					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	awesome	159	53.3	53.3	53.3
	much better	141	46.7	46.7	100
	Total	300	100	100	

The results are showing the popularity of an ad in front of viewers, the highest rating achieved from the candidates who praised overall quality of an ad is 53.3% having the frequency of 48, and those who praised that it was better presentation were 46.7% having the frequency of 42 we can consider that the advertisement can plays vital role to effect towards to achieves customer satisfaction.

Point of an appeal & favorite thing about the ad					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	celebrity	113	37.8	37.8	37.8
	music	100	33.3	33.3	71.1
	message	87	28.9	28.9	100
	Total	300	100	100	

This results are nearly in collision with each other, mostly candidates have voted Celebrity having percentage of 37.8%, about the Music 33.3% & the message is conveying with an ad 28.9%.

There were eleven more questions specifically design to test the hypotheses of the study. These statements are made on likert scale. The responses of the respondents were statistically tested via one sample T test using SPSS 17. The results of the study have been summarized in following table.

Table 1 Results of One-Sample Test				
Hypo No	Survey Questions	N	Sig. Value	Mean Difference
1	The highly creative Ads are also highly successful	300	0.00	0.15667
2	Consumers have favorable response to the Advertisement efforts	300	0.00	0.134364
3	There is Honesty in Ads i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads	300	0.07	0.106667
4	H4: The highly attractive Ads are also highly successful.	300	0.01	-0.05667
5	The Ads attracts the perception and makes customer sense of comfortable	300	0.00	0.8333
6	The Ads by firms in paint industry to Buy Decision	300	0.07	0.09667
7	Physical appearance of the product such as Packaging is highly attractive to induce for Buying	300	0.26	0.4667
8	The quality of the Product is on the same line as it appears in the Advertisement and Promotional efforts	300	0.00	0.519
9	Consumers are satisfied with the quality of the product	300	0.01	0.23333
10	Consumers are comfortable with the price of the product	300	0.00	-0.256
11	The Advertisement has filled gap between consumers and the management of the company	300	0.00	0.354

H1: The highly creative Ads are also highly successful.

The first statement in the above table has been used to test the first hypothesis. The sig value is less than 0.05 but the mean difference (0.156) is positive; which shows that respondents highly agree that the highly successful ads by firms in paint industry are highly creative.

H2: Consumers have favorable response to the Advertisement efforts

The second hypothesis has also been highly agreed because the mean difference (0.1343) is positive and sig value is less than 0.05. It signifies that the respondents agree that Consumers have favorable response to the Advertisement efforts.

H3: There is Honesty in Ads i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads

The third statement in the above table has been used to test the third hypothesis. The sig value is less than 0.05 but the mean difference (0.1066) is positive; which shows that respondents highly agree that there is Honesty in Ads i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads.

H4: The highly attractive Ads are also highly successful.

On the other side the respondents did not show their consent with the statement that Ads by firms in paint industry are more attractive than its competitors. The result of one sample T test provides that sig value is less 0.05 and the mean difference (-0.05667) is negative. It suggests that respondents did not agree with statement.

H5: The Ads attracts the perception and makes appeal to buy it

The respondents showed their consent with the statement that Ads attracts the perception and makes appeal to buy it. The result of one sample T test provides that sig value (0.26) is more 0.05 and the mean difference (0.4667) is positive. It suggests that respondents agree with statement.

H6: The Ads by firms in paint industry induces to Buy Decision

The sixth hypothesis has also been highly agreed because the mean difference (0.09667) is positive and sig value (0.07) is greater than 0.05. It signifies that the respondents agree that Ads by firms in paint industry induces to buy Decision.

H7: Physical appearance of the product such as Packaging is highly attractive to induce for Buying

The seventh Hypothesis has also been highly agreed because the mean difference (0.1343) is positive and sig value is less than 0.05. It signifies that the respondents agree that Physical appearance of the product such as Packaging is highly attractive to induce for Buying.

H8: The quality of the Product is on the same line as it appears in the Advertisement and Promotional efforts

The respondents showed their consent with the statement that quality of the Product is on the same line as it appears in the Advertisement and Promotional efforts. The result of one sample T test provides that sig value (0.00) is less than 0.05 but the mean difference (0.516) is positive. It suggests that respondents agree with statement.

H9: Consumers are satisfied with the quality of the product

The respondents showed their consent with the statement that Ads attracts the perception and makes appeal to buy it. The result of one sample T test provides that sig value (0.26) is more 0.05 and the mean difference (0.233) is positive. It suggests that respondents agree with statement.

H10: Consumers are comfortable with the price of the product

On the other side the respondents did not show their consent with the statement that Consumers are comfortable with the price of the product. The result of one sample T test provides that sig value is less 0.05 and the mean difference (-0.256) is negative. It suggests that respondents did not agree with statement.

H11: The Advertisement has filled gap between consumers and the management of the company

The eleventh statement in the above table has been used to test the eleventh hypothesis. The sig value is less than 0.05 but the mean difference (0.354) is positive; which shows that respondents highly agree that the Advertisement has filled gap between consumers and the management of the company.

Discussion

The results of one sample T test have technically been discussed. The general view of the findings is needed to be discussed. The results suggest that respondents highly agree that the ads by firms in paint industry are highly creative and that Consumers have favorable response to the Advertisement efforts. The respondents further expressed their high consent that there is Honesty in Ads i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads. Besides, it is also agreed that Ads attracts the perception and makes appeal to buy it. The study suggests that the respondents agree that Ads by firms in paint industry induces to buy Decision and that Physical appearance of the product such as Packaging is highly attractive to induce for Buying. The respondents showed their consent with the statement that quality of the Product is on the same line as it appears in the Advertisement and Promotional efforts. The respondents showed their consent with the statement that Ads attracts the perception and makes appeal to buy it. It is also being agreed that the ads by firms in paint industry are highly creative.

However, on the other side the respondents did not show their consent with the statement that Consumers are comfortable with the price of the product. Moreover respondents did not show their consent with the statement that Ads by a firm are more attractive than its competitors.

Conclusion

The study has concluded that Advertisement made by firms in paint industry has positive effect on the growth of sales revenue. The survey based study has concluded that the advertisements made by firms in paint industry are highly creative and effective in inducing buyers' sales decision. It has been concluded that advertisement effectiveness can be acquired by being honest in Advertisement i.e. level of quality is same as it is expressed in their Ads. The effective Advertisement efforts can lead to Growth in sales. However, the respondents do not appear comfortable with price being charged by by firms in paint industry paint.

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